

UZBEKISTAN-KOREA: CURRENT AND PROSPECTS OF
MUTUAL COOPERATION

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**ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДИАЛЕКТОВ КОРЕЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ПО
КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ**

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Аннотация: Диалект представляет собой одну из самых используемых систем речевого общения в корейском языке, являясь особенным средством, позволяющим установить контакт с собеседником. Исследование диалектов, в частности диалектов корейского языка, является неопределимым маркером развития любого языка, его зарождения и исторического развития, а также даёт возможность проследить за изменением и становлением слов, существующих в современной форме языка. Кроме того, диалекты позволяют проникнуть в суть различных социальных и культурных пластов, составляющих языковой социум. Языки и диалекты живут и развиваются в непрерывном и тесном взаимодействии, которое оказывает влияние на все стороны и уровни взаимодействующих языков.

Ключевые слова: Литературный корейский, географическое распространение, пхеньянский диалект, диалект юкчи, диалект Хамген, Коре Мар, Коре Сарам.

**KOREYS TILI DIALEKTLARINING TASNIFI BO‘YICHA
XUSUSIYATLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Dialekt koreys tilida eng ko‘p ishlatiladigan nutq aloqa tizimlaridan biri bo‘lib, suhbatdosh bilan aloqa o‘rnatish uchun maxsus vosita hisoblanadi. Dialektlarni, xususan, koreys tilining dialektlarini o‘rganish har qanday tilning rivojlanishi, uning kelib chiqishi va tarixiy rivojlanishining bebaho belgisidir, shuningdek, tilning zamonaviy shaklida mavjud bo‘lgan so‘zlarning o‘zgarishi va shakllanishini kuzatishga imkon beradi. Bundan

tashqari, dialektlar til jamiyatini tashkil etuvchi turli xil ijtimoiy va madaniy qatlamlarning mohiyatiga kirishga imkon beradi. Tillar va lahjalar o'zaro ta'sir qiluvchi tillarning barcha tomonlari va darajalariga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan doimiy va yaqin o'zaro ta'sirda yashaydi va rivojlanadi.

Asosiy so'z va tushunchalar: Adabiy koreys tili, geografik taqsimot, Pxenyang shevasi, Yukchi shevasi, Xamgen shevasi, Koryo Mar, Koryo saram.

FEATURES OF DIALECTS OF THE KOREAN LANGUAGE ACCORDING TO THE CLASSIFICATION

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Abstarct: Dialect is one of the most used systems of speech communication in the Korean language, being a special means to establish contact with the interlocutor. The study of dialects, in particular dialects of the Korean language, is an invaluable marker of the development of any language, its origin and historical development, and also makes it possible to trace the change and formation of words existing in the modern form of the language. In addition, dialects allow you to get into the essence of the various social and cultural layers that make up the linguistic society. Languages and dialects live and develop in continuous and close interaction, which affects all sides and levels of interacting languages.

Keywords: Literary Korean, geographical distribution, Pyongyang dialect, Yukchi dialect, Hamgyong dialect, Kore Mar, Kore Saram.

A dialect is called a variation of a certain language, where a group of people is connected by a territorial, professional or social community, who are in constant and direct language contact. It is considered to be a kind of language used by the association of people in a particular speech community.

The Korean language has several dialects throughout the Korean peninsula². The relief of the peninsula is mainly mountainous, and the "territory" of each of the dialects approximately corresponds to geographical regions. However, geographical proximity does not always correlate with dialect: For historical reasons, the Yukchi dialect of the far north is more similar to the Pyongyang dialect than to the Hamgyong dialect surrounding it. Most of the dialects are named after the names of the provinces of Korea.

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² <https://www.worldatlas.com/>

Due to its wide geographical distribution in different regions and among different speakers, the features of the dialect may vary and differ to varying degrees from the literary Korean language. Koremar³ is not a native language for Koreans deported to Central Asia, and they speak South Korean dialects. Nowadays, most Kore-Sarams⁴ have switched to Russian, and at best Koremar is a second language for them. Only a small number of representatives of the older generation actively use it to this day. Because of this, the dialect is in danger of extinction.

The formation and development of dialects of the Korean language has been going on for many centuries. Now there are six main dialects: northeast (including the Korean dialects of Northeast China and Hamgyong Province), northwest (prov. Pyeongan and part of Hwanghae), and central (Seoul, prov. Gyeonggi, North Chuncheon, part of Gangwon and Hwanghae provinces), southeastern (prov. Gyeongsang and part of the prov. Gangwon), southwest (prov. Cholla and part of the prov. South Chuncheon) and the dialect of Jeju. The differences in dialects relate mainly to vocabulary and phonetics, to a lesser extent grammar. As a result of the language policy of rationing and forming literary standards and the changed lifestyle of modern society in both parts of Korea, dialects are being squeezed out of many spheres, and they are being used more and more only in everyday speech. The development of the Korean language cannot be understood without taking into account the long and sometimes powerful political and cultural influence of China, as clearly evidenced by both written Korean and oral speech.

Many researchers tend to believe that over 60% of Korean words are of Chinese origin. The Korean language has been used colloquially for centuries and until the middle of the XV century. The common people in the country did not have their own national script. At the same time, there was a written and literary language – Hanmun. Hanmun had a supra-dialect character⁵, and it preceded the national literary language. Unlike the Chinese hieroglyphic script of the Wenyang, which was used in official documentation, historical chronicles, and diplomatic correspondence of old Korea, Hanmun was and remained the language of culture and education until the end of the XIX century. The last quarter of the XIX century was marked in Korea by a powerful educational movement and the rapid spread of Christianity in Korea. Hundreds of schools were opened in the country, clubs and societies were created that covered wide

³ Kore mar is the language of Koreans (Koresaram, Soviet / Russian Koreans), existing mainly in oral form and functioning only in the family and household sphere.

⁴ Kore-saram is the self—name of the majority of ethnic Koreans in the post-Soviet space.

⁵ It is used in two distinctive contexts, describing structural or functional relations within a particular language.

segments of the population. Bibles, textbooks, newspapers were printed. On this educational wave, which coincided with the awakening of national consciousness and the growth of anti-Japanese sentiments, the Korean language and the national script, which was then called Kunmun, began to be widely used in the fields of education, literature and science. An important role in the introduction and wide dissemination of the Korean national letter was played by the outstanding linguist and patriot Chu Si Kyung, who gave it a new name "hangul". The publication of large circulations of the daily newspapers of the mass newspapers "Dongailbo" and "Chosonilbo» had a significant impact on the development of uniform norms of the Korean language. It is generally believed that by the early 1930s, a "literary language" or "standard language" (Pyejunmal) was formed in Korea, based on the Seoul version of the central dialect. Scientists note that the 25-year colonial rule of Japan, the forced assimilation policy, which reached the point of stick repression for the use of the native language, did not leave a clearly tangible "Japanese trace" in the Korean language, although, of course, they largely restrained the development of a single literary language. The formation of two Korean states after the Second World War, the fratricidal bloody war and the split of the country inevitably led to different ways of language construction. Since vocabulary is the most variable in the language, today there is a significant difference in vocabulary, especially with regard to neologisms, terms, primarily socio-political. It is not difficult to guess that a lot of borrowings from English and Americanisms have entered the South Korean press and literature, and over time into the spoken language. In North Korea, it must be assumed that they also used not only Soviet material and financial assistance, but also the experience of socialist construction, which, of course, required appropriate ideologized terms - borrowings from the Russian language. What has been said fully applies to the German language in the former GDR and Germany, but in separate German states there has always been (only with an insignificant difference) a single spelling and writing, which cannot be said about the states separated by the 38th parallel. While North Korea has completely abandoned the "reactionary, anti-people" hieroglyphs, in the South they continue to be widely used. To see the difference between the two Korean states, it is enough to look not only at the shop windows, but also at their signs, that is, what is written and how.

The dialect used by the Korean community in the Yanbian Autonomous Prefecture of China in Manchuria may be included in the Hamgyong dialects, since their mutual similarity is due to the early immigration of Hamgyong people to the area and their subsequent language contact. The language spoken by

Koreans in Central Asia, that is, in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, developed from the Yukchin dialect, which is part of the Hamgyong dialects, but it has many archaic forms, as well as innovations compared to the original Yukchin dialects.(King 1992).In addition to regional dialects, North Korean and South Korean exhibit significant linguistic divergence resulting from the division of North and South in 1945 and the subsequent Korean War in 1950.In this section we will look at dialect differences in the Korean language, characteristic phonological isoglosses ⁶, typical features of each dialect and linguistic differences between the North and South Korean languages. In the main part of the text, we transcribe all Korean words in Yale Romanization, but Korean proper names are transcribed in the McCune-Reischauer system in accordance with generally accepted practice. In addition, we also use a slightly modified version of phonetic symbols for some linguistic/phonetic examples when needed. Dialect subzones can be classified by determining the isogloss of certain phonological features and morphological and grammatical features, as well as lexical features. Based on the distributions, it is possible to establish many dialect sub domains, but two or more dialect regions may overlap in certain features.

At this point in time, there are only two types of dialects – social and territorial. Social dialects are characterized by the presence of certain lexical features, but they do not contain a grammatical and phonetic structure. Phonetics and grammar in it does not have distinctive features from the structure of the literary language or dialects, of which they are a branch. The most common type of dialect is territorial, or otherwise called regional. As a rule, the speech of one locality is not much different from any other place in the same country. Territorial dialects have their own phonetic and grammatical structure, and are also practically the only means of communication for speakers of these dialects.

For the first time, the question of the origin of the Korean language was raised in the XIX century by Western scientists, when the first contacts between Korea and other countries were established. Then there were various theories according to which the Korean language was related to the Ural-Altai, Tibetan, Tungusic-Manchurian, Japanese and other languages.

The theory of the genetic relationship⁷ of the Korean language with the Altai family of languages was the most popular among linguists engaged in

⁶ An isogloss. also called a heterogloss (see Etymology below), is the geographic boundary of a certain linguistic feature, such as the pronunciation of a vowel, the meaning of a word, or the use of some morphological or syntactic feature.

⁷ Kim G. N. Where did the Korean language come from and how did it develop, Professor, Doctor of Historical Sciences. <https://koryo-saram.ru>

comparative linguistics. Most likely, supporters of this theory were attracted by the fact that both the Korean language and the Altaic languages belong to agglutinative languages. During agglutination, derived words and grammatical forms are formed by attaching to the root of service particles - affixes (prefixes, infixes, suffixes), which conjugate with each other without undergoing significant sound changes. In agglutinative languages, which include all Turkic languages, each affix has only one grammatical meaning, for example, numbers or cases. The most important ⁸ common features of the Korean and Altaic languages are further the euphony of vowels, the absence of relative pronouns and conjunctions, the alternation of consonants and vowels. Another characteristic feature is the restriction of consonantism⁹ at the beginning of a word, meaning that certain consonants (consonants) cannot stand at the beginning of a word, for example, initially there were no words beginning with "r" and "b" in Korean and Altaic languages. The theory of the common origin of the Korean and Japanese languages arose at the turn of the XIX and XX centuries as a result of attempts to find out the genealogy of the latter. A set of common features of Korean with the Altaic languages is valid for the Japanese language, with the exception of the sign of consonance of vowels. The structural similarity of the Korean and Japanese languages is more than obvious, which cannot be said in lexico-grammatical terms. Lee Ki-moon, a well-known researcher of the history of the Korean language, notes that linguists counted only about 200 words and 15 endings very similar in both languages¹⁰. Thus, most modern linguists recognize the distant rather than close relationship of the Korean and Altaic languages. In contrast, the theory of close ties between three language groups is very common among them: Turkic, Mongolian and Tungusic. It can be assumed that they branched off from one common proto-language (Altaic). Now it is still difficult to answer the question: what kind of connection existed between the language that preceded Korean (Puesco - Khan proto-language) and ancient Altaic. It is possible that Puesco-Khan is a branch of the Altaic proto-language or that they both go back to an older common language.

For a long time, the Korean language has been divided into two groups: the northern - "puyosky" and the southern "Hanska"¹¹. The language of the first group was spoken by tribes living in Manchuria and North Korea. In the north

⁸ <http://ru.wikipedai.org/wiki>

⁹ <http://ru.wikipedai.org/wiki>

¹⁰ Anikina V.V. The place of the Korean language in the genealogical classification of languages: European, Oriental approach //Scientific article. <http://docplayer.ru/49281036-Mesto-koreyskogo-yazyka-v-genealogicheskoy-klassifikacii-yazykov-evropeyskiy-vostochnyy-podhody-v-v-anikina.html>

¹¹ The tree of the origin of the languages of the world according to the ideas of the Moscow school at the end of the 2nd millennium BC, see http://pikabu.ru/story/derevo_proiskhojdeniya_yazikov_mira.

of the peninsula there were early feudal states of Puyo, Goguryeo, and Okcho, of which the leading role was occupied by Goguryeo¹². The "khan" language was spoken by South Korean tribes who founded three khan states: Chhinhan, Mahan iPhehan. Chinhan, the strongest of these three states, was founded by the kingdom of Silla, which, in alliance with Tang China, subjugated the state of Baekje in the southwest in 660 and Goguryeo in the north in 668. The creation of the unified State of Silla was a major event in the history of Korea¹³. In the VII-VIII centuries. Silla has become a powerful centralized state. It was headed by Wang (the king), who relied on the administrative apparatus, which included the central departments in the capital and the official network of the country, divided into 9 regions and 400 districts. Agriculture, the basis of the economic system, as well as handicrafts and trade, successfully developed in Silla. Significant progress has been made in science, education and culture. Oral folk art became widespread, classical fiction was born, especially lyrical poetry. As a result, the linguistic unity of the country was formed on the basis of the Silla language. At the end of the VII-beginning of the IX centuries. The state of Silla gradually tends to decline. The country is shaken by peasant uprisings and internecine strife. The new unification of the country was carried out by the famous commander Wang Gong, who proclaimed himself king of the Koryo state in 918, from which the modern name of Korea originated. The political and cultural center of the new state education was moved to the city of Kaesong, located in the middle part of the peninsula. Thus, the Kaesong dialect has become the norm of the unified national language of the country. In 1392, the famous commander and politician Lee Seongye overthrew the last king of the Koryo state and proclaimed himself king of a new dynasty that ruled Korea until 1910. The capital of the Joseon State, named in memory of the ancient Joseon, was moved to the small city of Hanseong, later renamed Seoul. Since geographically the new capital was located near Kaesong, the formation of a unified Korean language continued its further development.

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¹² Kim G. D.I.N., Professor, Director of the Center for Korean Studies of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University. //Scientific article. <http://www.koryosaram.freenet.kz>

¹³ Kim G. D.I.N., Professor, Director of the Center for Korean Studies of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University. //Scientific article. <http://www.koryosaram.freenet.kz>

(prov. Cholla and part of the prov. South Chuncheon) and the dialect of Jeju¹⁴. The differences in dialects relate mainly to vocabulary and phonetics, to a lesser extent grammar. As a result of the language policy of rationing and forming literary standards and the changed lifestyle of modern society in both parts of Korea, dialects are being squeezed out of many spheres, and they are being used more and more only in everyday speech. The development of the Korean language cannot be understood without taking into account the long and sometimes powerful political and cultural influence of China, as clearly evidenced by both written Korean and oral speech. Many researchers tend to believe that over 60% of Korean words are of Chinese origin¹⁵. The Korean language has been used colloquially for centuries and until the middle of the XV century. The common people in the country did not have their own national script. At the same time, there was a written and literary language – 한문 [hanmun]¹⁶. Hanmun had a supra-dialect character, and it preceded the national literary language. Unlike the Chinese hieroglyphic script of the Wenyang, which was used in official documentation, historical chronicles, and diplomatic correspondence of old Korea, Hanmun was and remained the language of culture and education until the end of the XIX century. The last quarter of the XIX century was marked in Korea by a powerful educational movement and the rapid spread of Christianity in Korea. Hundreds of schools were opened in the country, clubs and societies were created that covered wide segments of the population. Bibles, textbooks, newspapers were printed. On this educational wave, which coincided with the awakening of national consciousness and the growth of anti-Japanese sentiments, the Korean language and the national script, which was then called Kunmun¹⁷, began to be widely used in the fields of education, literature and science. An important role in the introduction and wide dissemination of the Korean national letter was played by the outstanding linguist and patriot Chu Si Kyung, who gave it a new name 한글 [hangyl]. The publication of large circulations of daily newspapers mass newspapers [Dong'aillb] and 조선읽어 [Josonilbo], had a significant impact on the development of uniform norms of the Korean language. It is generally believed that by the early 1930s, a "literary language" or "standard language" (편준말 [pyejunmal])¹⁸ was formed in Korea, based on the Seoul version of the central

¹⁴<http://ru.wikipedai.org/wiki>

¹⁵<https://sites.google.com/site/stvvvyaz/studenty-2014/dialekty/dialekty-korejskogo-azyka-korotkov-pavel>

¹⁶Vasiliev A.A. Features of dialects of North Korea // Bulletin of the Korean Language and Culture Center: Issue 8. St. Petersburg: Publishing House of St. Petersburg State University, 2005. - pp.10-32.

¹⁷ Park Chihon Research and a translation with comments. Hongminchon. - Seoul, 1984

¹⁸ Where did the Korean language come from and how did it develop? See <http://korea.narod.ru/content/korea/>

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After analyzing this topic, we can conclude that a lot of borrowings from English and Americanisms have entered the South Korean press and literature, and over time into the spoken language. In North Korea, it must be assumed that they also used not only Soviet material and financial assistance, but also the experience of socialist construction, which, of course, required appropriate ideologized terms - borrowings from the Russian language.

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